

The modern methods of teaching English to students

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Abstract: In many parts of the world, there is a growing interest in modern methods of teaching English to students, the question of how to do it - how the curriculum, subject, topic and methodology should differ from the previously developed familiar norms gives birth.

Keywords: Teaching methods, innovations, methodology, skills, dialogical speech, reading strategies.

Introduction: The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of Teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on Modern Methods of Teaching English has been limited. Nowadays many books and articles are written to attract attention to this point. In planning curricular and methods it has been suggested that an understanding of Students and their needs, interest, abilities, likes, dislikes, and developmental status should take precedence over other considerations.

Methodology: Known to us, using innovations and new pedagogical technologies are resulting well. Sometimes using same styles in teaching language may let go down interests of student to language. We advise some types of teaching in use, not to go down interest to foreign language.

1. Dialogical speech- in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach. “Modern Methodology of Teaching English puts Speaking in Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give an opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech”. More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness.

2. Student reads the text himself and tells the meaning. Reading is interactive. Reading short stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Uzbek, English and American writers is very important in language learning

3. Understanding by listening - by these way students can improve speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity. Comprehension of speech while listening mainly based on auditory feelings. By perceiving, reproduce what we hear, in the form of inwardly speech. Listening comprehension is impossible without working of speech motor analyzer. Of course internal speaking requires ability to speak in this language.

4. Learning English through the watching movies. Nowadays, teachers take into consideration students' demands for watching real movie stories together with reading books, magazines and newspapers. Because, as it is known not only printed materials can serve as a great source of teaching but also songs and movies play a key role in learning foreign languages.

5. The importance of teaching Vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language to be taught in the institutes. In addition to learn new vocabulary, learner need to able to use strategies to cope with unknown vocabulary met in listening or reading text, to make up for gaps in productive vocabulary in speaking and writing to gain fluency in using known vocabulary and to learn new words in isolation. Vocabulary learning is not on end in itself. A rich vocabulary makes to perform the skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing easier. By the type of teaching in traditional style is divided into several aspects such as speaking, analytic reading, reading at home, practice grammar, practical phonetics.

Discussion: There are three teaching methods that dominate the business of language instruction: the Direct Method, the Grammar-Translation Method, and the Audio-Lingual Method. Deciding which is the best method is difficult because each has strengths and weaknesses, and the nature of a student's goals will

determine which is best for that student. Although many language-training sources may speak about exclusive or unique approaches, with few exceptions they are using one of these three methods. We conducted extensive research on the subject of teaching methods for our online language training programs. Here is a description of the three primary language teaching methods along with our analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of each one:

The Direct Method:

The Direct Method is also known as the Oral or Natural method. It's based on the active involvement of the student in both speaking and listening to the new language in realistic everyday situations. The process consists of a gradual acquisition of grammatical structure and vocabulary. The learner is encouraged to think in the

target language rather than translate. He or she hears and uses the language before seeing it written.

The Grammar-Translation Method

This method grew from the traditional method of teaching Latin and Greek. The method is based on analysis of the written language using translation exercises, reading comprehension and written imitation of texts. Learning mainly involves the mastery of grammatical rules and memorization of vocabulary lists.

The Audio-Lingual Method

This self-teaching method is also known as the Aural-Oral method. The learning is based on repetition of dialogues and phrases about every day situations. These phrases are imitated, repeated, and drilled to make the response automatic. Reading and writing are both reinforcements of what the learner practices.

Conclusion: A key strategy for teaching English is likely to be to create a positive and supportive work environment, offering a variety of challenges suitable for different levels. It must be said that it is virtually impossible to use only one method or approach to effectively teach a second language. Classes should be designed using effective teaching methods. This is how we successfully achieve our goals in education.

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